

Evaluating Whether AI Has Reached Human-Level Reasoning in Insurance Decision Making

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Abstract

AI is increasingly being used in insurance for faster claim processing and fraud detection. However, its accuracy depends on the quality of input data. This study analyzes how AI systems and human surveyors respond to a technically invalid insurance scenario. The case involved a claim where rust was observed on a plastic bumper, which is not possible in real life.

The results show a clear difference in how humans and AI think. Human surveyors quickly identified the technical flaw and rejected the case, while AI systems assumed the input was correct and continued solving it. Most AI models gave decisions like “Not Fraud” or “Can be Both” based on policy rules and lack of proof, even though the situation itself was impossible.

This highlights the concept of Garbage In Garbage Out (GIGO), where incorrect input leads to incorrect output (Awati, 2023). The study also shows that AI is not just making logical mistakes, but it can be influenced by misleading information such as false claims or legal arguments.

Another important finding is that if AI cannot detect simple errors like this, then more complex real world cases will be even harder to handle. Human surveyors act as a filter who stop invalid input before it affects the decision, while AI lacks this ability.

The study concludes that AI has not yet reached human-level reasoning and should be used with human supervision for better accuracy and fairness.

Introduction

AI is now used in many areas for decision making, including insurance claims. It helps companies process claims faster and detect fraud. But for correct results, the system must have correct input and proper reasoning.

One important idea is Garbage In Garbage Out or GIGO. It means if the input is wrong, the output will also be wrong. For example, if incorrect data is given, the result will not be reliable (Awati, 2023).

In insurance, trained professionals called surveyors check damages and assess claims. These surveyors are licensed by the Insurance Regulatory and Development Authority of India,

which regulates insurance in India and protects policy holders (IRDAI, 2021). A license means they are qualified to inspect and assess properly.

However, AI systems may assume that the input is correct. They depend on patterns and data, but they do not truly understand the situation. AI lacks common sense and real world understanding, which can lead to mistakes when the input itself is wrong (Levis, 2024).

The objective of this study is to evaluate whether AI has reached human-level reasoning in insurance decision making by comparing its responses with experienced surveyors.

Problem Statement

In motor insurance claims, correct decisions depend on facts and technical correctness. In this case, a car owner reported damage to the front bumper and rust was found in that area.

Rust is a process where iron reacts with oxygen and water to form iron oxide. This happens in metals like iron and steel and usually takes time depending on moisture and conditions (Steele, 2022).

However, the front bumper of modern cars is made of plastic, and plastic does not rust. So the situation given in the case is not possible in real life.

This case also includes misleading elements such as possible false claims and legal arguments based on lack of proof. These factors act as “garbage input”.

According to GIGO, even if the reasoning is correct, the result will still be wrong if the input is faulty (Awati, 2023).

The main question in this study is whether AI can identify such invalid situations like human experts, or whether it continues solving based on incorrect assumptions.

Case Scenario

The following case was given to all participants without any changes:

Motor Insurance Claim Evaluation

A car owner files a claim for a front bumper accident on a Honda City (2018 model), saying it happened yesterday.

Inspection report says there is rust around the damaged area of the front bumper.

The customer says the rust came because of recent rain and poor paint quality.

But weather records show there was no heavy rain in that time.

The customer shows photos with no damage 2 days before, but there is no metadata so it cannot be verified.

A mechanic says rust usually takes many days or weeks to form.

There are no past inspection records of the car.

The policy says if there is no clear proof of fraud, benefit of doubt can be given to the customer.

A lawyer says there is no proper proof that the damage is old.

Methodology

This study uses a simple comparison method to evaluate how humans and AI respond to a technically invalid insurance case. The aim was not only to compare answers, but also to understand how each one thinks and whether they can detect incorrect input.

Two human surveyors were included in this study. Both are licensed by the Insurance Regulatory and Development Authority of India and have more than 15 years of experience in motor insurance claims, making them domain experts. Their role in real life is to inspect damage and make fair and practical decisions.

- Nitin Arora (FIII), Zonal Manager Motor Claims at Zurich Kotak General Insurance
- Sourabh Juneja, Surveyor and Loss Assessor

Both surveyors were given the same case without any changes.

For AI, these systems were used: ChatGPT, Google Gemini, Meta AI, Perplexity AI and DuckDuckGo AI. All systems were used without logging in to ensure neutral responses.

The responses were compared based on:

- whether they checked if the case is valid
- how they handled misleading or incomplete information
- what final decision they gave

This method helps to identify whether the system can act as a filter to reject incorrect input, or whether it continues reasoning even when the base information is wrong.

Collected Data

This section includes the raw responses collected from human surveyors and AI systems. No changes have been made to the original answers.

Surveyor 1

"Invalid question as the bumper is a plastic parts and it will not catch rust."

Surveyor 2

"Beta first of all this question itself is not right as bumper is a plastic part and plastic doesn't get rust formations, so in question, use any metal part, instead of front bumper. But beta if you want observation metal parts ke hisaab se, I can share that."

ChatGPT response:

Decision: Can be Both

Reason:

There are strong indicators of possible misrepresentation—especially the presence of rust, which typically develops over several days to weeks, and the lack of supporting weather conditions. These suggest the damage may predate the reported accident. However, there is no conclusive proof of fraud: the photos (though unverifiable), absence of prior inspection records, and policy clause favoring the insured in unclear cases create reasonable doubt. Therefore, the case cannot be definitively classified as fraud.

Gemini response:

Claim Evaluation Summary

Decision: Not Fraud (Strictly within the context of the specific policy clause provided)

Reasoning:

While the technical evidence strongly suggests the damage is not new, the decision hinges on the specific wording of the insurance policy.

- The Technical Evidence: Rust formation is an oxidation process that generally requires a significant period of exposure. Scientific consensus and the mechanic's testimony indicate that rust cannot form overnight, even with rain. The formula for iron oxide (rust) is generally represented as:

This chemical reaction is a gradual process; the absence of rainfall further debunking the claimant's "recent rain" theory.

- The Legal/Policy Constraint: The policy explicitly states that "benefit of doubt" must be given to the insured in the "absence of conclusive fraud evidence."
- The Gap in Proof: Because the photo metadata is missing and there are no prior inspection records (pre-existing condition reports), the insurer cannot conclusively prove when the damage occurred. Suspicion, however strong, does not constitute "conclusive evidence" in a legal or contractual sense.

Conclusion:

Under the provided clause, the lawyer's argument holds more weight than the technical suspicion. Without a "smoking gun" (like a prior repair estimate or verified dated photo), the insurer is contractually obligated to favor the insured.

Meta AI response:

Decision: Not Fraud

Reason: Although there are inconsistencies in the customer's claim and circumstantial evidence suggests the rust may have been pre-existing (weather records, mechanic's statement), the policy explicitly states that in the absence of *conclusive* fraud evidence, the benefit of doubt may be given to the insured. There isn't definitive proof that the damage is old or that the customer is intentionally defrauding.

Perplexity AI:

Decision: Not Fraud (Benefit of doubt applies)

Reason

While significant red flags suggest pre-existing damage, the evidence is circumstantial, not conclusive:

- **Rust Timeline Mismatch:** A mechanic confirms rust formation typically takes several days to weeks, contradicting the customer's claim that it appeared from "yesterday's" accident and recent rain. Surface rust can appear in 48–72 hours under ideal wet conditions, but weather records show no significant rainfall in Delhi during that period to accelerate this process.
- **Unverified Photos:** The photos provided by the customer lack metadata and cannot be authenticated, rendering them inadmissible as definitive proof of the vehicle's prior condition.
- **Policy Clause & Legal Standard:** The policy explicitly states that in the absence of conclusive fraud evidence, the benefit of doubt must be given to the insured. The lawyer correctly argues that while the rust makes the claim suspicious, there is no forensic proof (e.g., a prior inspection report or verified timestamped image) definitively proving the damage existed before the alleged accident date.

Conclusion: The claim is highly suspicious and likely involves an attempt to claim old damage, but without definitive proof (like a prior repair invoice or authenticated photo), the insurer must adhere to the policy clause and treat it as Not Fraud for settlement purposes, though likely with a deduction for the pre-existing rust portion if quantifiable.

DuckDuckGo AI response:

Decision: Can be Both

Reason

- Evidence supporting non-fraud: recent photos (albeit unverifiable) show no damage two days earlier; policy favors insured absent conclusive fraud proof.
- Evidence supporting fraud/older damage: inspector observed rust at the damaged area; mechanic says rust typically takes days–weeks; no rainfall corroboration for customer's explanation; no metadata or prior inspections to independently verify timeline.
- Conclusion: available evidence is ambiguous and conflicting, so a definitive finding cannot be made; recommend conditional outcome (provisionally pay subject to recovery of parts/repair verification or further forensic inspection such as paint/rust lab testing or authenticated image metadata) or escalate for deeper investigation.

Comparative Analysis

This section compares how AI systems and human surveyors answered the same case using the tables below.

Table 1: Comparison of AI Models

Parameter	ChatGPT	Google Gemini	Meta AI	Perplexity AI	DuckDuckGo AI
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Decision	Can be Both	Not Fraud	Not Fraud	Not Fraud	Can be Both
Approach Style	Balanced, cautious	Technical + policy-driven	Short, policy-focused	Analytical, evidence-heavy	Balanced, suggests investigation
Use of Technical Evidence	Yes (rust timeline)	Strong (chemical explanation + science)	Moderate	Strong (timeline + conditions)	Moderate
Consideration of Policy Clause	Yes	Strong emphasis	Strong emphasis	Strong emphasis	Yes
Handling of Uncertainty	Accepts ambiguity	Resolves via policy	Resolves via policy	Resolves via policy	Keeps case open
Assumption of Premise Validity	Yes (missed flaw)	Yes (missed flaw)	Yes (missed flaw)	Yes (missed flaw)	Yes (missed flaw)

All AI systems followed almost the same pattern. They assumed the case is correct and started solving it directly. Most of them focused on rust, weather and policy rules. Because there was no clear proof, most gave the answer as “Not Fraud”, while some said “Can be Both”.

One important thing is that none of the AI systems checked if the case is even possible. They did not notice that the plastic bumper cannot rust. They just continued solving based on the given info, which is kind of a big mistake.

Table 2: Comparison of Human Surveyors

Parameter	Surveyor 1	Surveyor 2
Initial Reaction	Rejects question	Rejects question
Identification of Technical Flaw	Yes (plastic doesn't rust)	Yes (plastic doesn't rust)
Approach Style	Direct, concise	Explanatory, corrective
Willingness to Proceed	No	Yes (if corrected to metal part)
Focus Area	Technical validity	Technical validity + practical correction
Assumption of Premise Validity	No (questions premise)	No (questions premise)

Both surveyors first checked the basic facts of the case. They quickly saw that the bumper is plastic and plastic does not rust. Because of this, they said the question itself is wrong.

Instead of solving it directly, they focused on the mistake in the question. One surveyor fully rejected it, while the other said it can be answered if we change it to a metal part. This shows they are thinking more practical and not just following the question blindly.

Overall Comparison

The main difference is in how they start thinking. AI systems directly try to solve the problem, while humans first check if the problem even makes sense or not.

This shows AI is good at logic and rules, but it can miss simple real world things. Humans may not always give long answers, but they can catch basic errors fast, which is actually very important.

Key Findings

- Human surveyors checked basic facts first
- Both surveyors identified that plastic cannot rust
- AI systems assumed the case was valid
- Most AI responses were “Not Fraud”
- AI focused on rules and policy instead of real world logic
- Humans used practical understanding
- AI gave detailed answers but missed a basic error
- Humans gave shorter answers but identified the core issue quickly
- AI is vulnerable to misleading input

Discussion

The results show that AI systems failed because they did not verify whether the situation was possible. They depended on input and applied logic without validation. This follows the idea of GIGO, where wrong input leads to wrong output (Awati, 2023).

The “garbage input” in this case included a technical impossibility, possible false claims, and legal arguments that ignored physical facts. AI systems accepted all of this and continued reasoning, showing lack of filtering ability.

AI models also have important limitations. They do not have real understanding or common sense and rely on patterns in data. Because of this, they may fail to detect impossible situations. They also depend heavily on data quality and struggle with real world context (Levis, 2024).

This creates risk in real insurance decisions. AI can be influenced by misleading inputs and may approve incorrect claims.

Human surveyors act as a validation layer. They inspect damage and make fair assessments using real world knowledge (ICICI Lombard, 2026). They were able to identify the mistake immediately.

Another key point is that if AI cannot detect a simple error like this, then handling complex real world cases will be even more difficult. Insurance claims often involve multiple variables, so missing basic checks can lead to serious errors.

This shows that AI has not yet reached human-level reasoning and requires supervision.

Limitations

- Small sample size
- Only one scenario tested
- Slight variation in data collection

These factors limit generalization, but still provide useful insights.

Conclusion

This study shows that AI has not yet reached human-level reasoning in insurance decision making. Human surveyors are able to detect when a situation is not possible, while AI systems continue solving based on given input.

AI is strong in logical processing, but it depends on data and lacks real world understanding. This makes it vulnerable to incorrect or misleading input.

The study also shows that if AI fails in simple cases, more complex cases will be even harder to handle. Human surveyors act as a filter that prevents invalid input from affecting decisions.

Therefore, AI should not replace human experts but should be used as a supporting tool with proper supervision to ensure accurate and fair outcomes.

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